

PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12746358>

Abstract. *The article provides information on the reforms being carried out by the state in the development of entrepreneurship, the implementation of adopted programs and created opportunities.*

Keywords: *"Every family is an entrepreneur" State program, entrepreneurship, family business, family householding, innovation, financial support, economic growth, production, management.*

ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ СЕМЕЙНОГО ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА

Аннотация. *В статье представлена информация о реформах, проводимых государством в сфере развития предпринимательства, реализации принятых программ и созданных возможностях.*

Ключевые слова: *Государственная программа «Каждая семья – предприниматель», предпринимательство, семейный бизнес, семейное хозяйство, инновации, финансовая поддержка, экономический рост, производство, управление.*

INTRODUCTION

During the development of the years of independence, as in all industries, the family business sector has undergone great changes. Due to the fact that the main condition for the transition to market relations is the creation of legal and organizational conditions for the formation of a multi-level economy and a competitive environment, during this period much attention was paid to privatization and the development of business activities. One of the main factors in creating a market environment in the deepening of economic reforms was the development of small business. A lot of attention is also paid to family business, which is one of its various areas. Each family, while receiving a high level of profit, produces products and services necessary for society, creates new markets for the country, contributes to the employment of the population, other organizations and appears as a consumer of products and services created in families, contributes to the development of the country's economy by paying certain types of taxes. During the performance of these tasks, the scale and volume of small business and private sector in the

country's economy has grown significantly. The number of families engaged in family business and, accordingly, its share in the gross domestic product is increasing.[2]

In accordance with Article 1 of the Law "On Family Entrepreneurship", family entrepreneurship is an entrepreneurial activity carried out by family members at the risk and under their own property responsibility for the purpose of obtaining income (profit), at the discretion of its participants. is based on A family business can be established with or without a legal entity. The organizational and legal form of a family business, which is carried out by establishing a legal entity, is a family enterprise. Without establishing a legal entity, family business is carried out in accordance with the procedure established by law.

MAIN PART

A family enterprise is a small business entity established by its participants for the production and sale of goods on a voluntary basis, on the basis of shared or joint property of the participants, as well as on the basis of the property of each of the participants. The activity of a family business is based on the personal work of its participants. The family business operates only as a legal entity.

The authorized fund of a family enterprise is formed at the expense of money, securities, other assets, including property rights valued in money or other rights that can be transferred to another person. A single house (apartment) cannot be included in the charter fund of a family enterprise. The participants of the family enterprise independently determine the property that they will contribute to the charter fund of the family enterprise in the manner provided for in the enterprise's foundation contract.

The authorized fund of a family enterprise must not be less than ten times the amount of the minimum wage established by the legislation on the date of submission of documents for state registration of the enterprise.

The property of the family enterprise consists of the property contributed by the participants of the family enterprise to its charter fund, the property received at the expense of loans and credits, the income received from the sale of goods, the performance of works, and the provision of services and directed to the development of the family enterprise, it also includes property received at the expense of income, other funds not prohibited by law.

Analyzes conducted in the field of family entrepreneurship in our country and its regions attract the population to entrepreneurship, create new jobs, ensure employment, provide practical assistance to citizens trying to be self-employed, effective use of labor resources showed that there are still unused opportunities in such directions. "Each family is an entrepreneur" Program was

adopted in our country in order to correct this deficiency and to make effective use of unused opportunities.[1]

Among the main directions of the "Every family is an entrepreneur" program, the following were defined:

1. Allocating preferential loans to people who want to do business. Ensuring that they provide practical assistance at every stage of the organization and implementation of business activities. Such practical assistance is provided by all official organizations.

2. Teaching the population entrepreneurial skills and providing practical assistance in organizing a type of activity.

3. Creating additional jobs by providing practical assistance to business entities to expand their activities.

4. Providing financial support for the implementation of activities on micro-enterprises, small-scale production entities and households. Creating an opportunity for the population to earn additional income.

5. Organization of mini-clusters in neighborhoods. In this case, connecting families with less experience who are starting this type of activity to experienced entrepreneurs who have achieved positive results in the field of entrepreneurship.

6. Expanding the range of services provided to family entrepreneurs. Establishment of market infrastructure facilities, service and sales outlets that organize the sale of products produced by them.

7. Giving vacant land areas to newly established business entities. Creating additional jobs and sources of income for the population.

8. Identification of entrepreneurs operating without state registration and assistance in legalizing their activities.

Allocation of preferential loans to residents who decide to engage in entrepreneurship is carried out in the following amounts and by the following responsible organizations: Preferential loans in the amount of 150 times the minimum wage on the basis of the recommendations of the heads of sectors for the socio-economic development of the regions and community assemblies will be given.

Insurance policies, third-party guaranty, pledge of property purchased on credit, and guaranty of the State Fund for the Support of Entrepreneurial Activity under the Cabinet of Ministers to business entities that are registered and operating in the prescribed manner It is possible to allocate an interest loan in the amount of 1000 times the minimum wage.

When lending investment projects of business entities, preferential loans in the amount of more than 1,000 times the minimum wage can be allocated based on the types of provision established within the framework of legislation.[3]

The state fund for supporting the development of entrepreneurship under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan allocates compensation for covering interest costs and guarantees for loans allocated to business entities within the framework of the "Every family is an entrepreneur" program.

When family entrepreneurs are insured against the risk of non-return of preferential loans by commercial banks, the insurance fee is set at an amount of no more than 1.5 percent, and the insurance conditions are eased.

CONCLUSION

Despite the special attention paid to family business activities, there is a lot of work to be done in this area. In order to develop the works in this direction at a faster pace, it is required to bring the management activities in them to the current level. There are works that need to be done in the field of using modern management methods and principles, in the field of the procedure for using economic resources, and in the field of labor resources management.[2,4]

At the same time, the development of small business, family entrepreneurship, ensuring the employment of the population, increasing the efficiency of the financial support system for programs for women and young generation initiatives, as well as fundamentally improving the working methods of commercial banks with state participation and banking by increasing the popularity of its services, it is necessary to establish full-fledged partnership relations with broad segments of the population, small business and family business entities.

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